

Historical approaches to the development of administrative law in Jordan in the period 1970-2024: From the modernization of public administration to the use of artificial intelligence

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study was to analyze the historical evolution of administrative law in Jordan from 1970 to the present. The research methodology involved the use of historical analysis and hermeneutics method. The historical analysis revealed significant developments in the development of administrative law in Jordan from 1970 to the present. In particular, the period from 1970 to 2000 was broadly characterized by intense reforms aimed at modernizing public administration and legislation to promote social justice and economic growth. With the advent of digital technologies, from 2000 to 2024 there was a significant impact of artificial intelligence on administrative processes, generating new opportunities to optimize public management and improve the quality of services provided to citizens. In the global context, administrative law has also gone through a difficult path of adaptation to new challenges such as globalization and rapid technological change. It is concluded that, through constant adaptation and dialectical innovation, administrative law continues to provide effective and fair governance that meets the needs of modern society.

Keywords: Administrative law; Legal history; Artificial intelligence in law; Modernization of legislation; Political transformations in the Middle East.

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Aproximaciones históricas al desarrollo del derecho administrativo en Jordania en el periodo 1970-2024: De la modernización de la administración pública al uso de la inteligencia artificial

RESUMEN

El objetivo principal del estudio fue analizar la evolución histórica del derecho administrativo en Jordania, desde 1970 hasta la actualidad. La metodología de la investigación implicó el uso del método de análisis histórico y hermenéutica. El análisis histórico reveló avances significativos en el desarrollo del derecho administrativo en Jordania, desde 1970 hasta la actualidad. En particular, el período comprendido entre 1970 y 2000 se caracterizó en líneas generales por intensas reformas encaminadas a modernizar la administración pública y la legislación para promover la justicia social y el crecimiento económico. Con la llegada de las tecnologías digitales, del año 2000 al 2024 se produjo un importante impacto de la inteligencia artificial en los procesos administrativos, generando nuevas oportunidades para optimizar la gestión pública y mejorar la calidad de los servicios prestados a los ciudadanos. En el contexto global, el derecho administrativo también ha atravesado un difícil camino de adaptación a nuevos desafíos como la globalización y el rápido cambio tecnológico. Por estas razones, se concluye que, a través de una constante adaptación e innovación dialéctica, el derecho administrativo continúa brindando una gobernanza efectiva y justa que satisface las necesidades de la sociedad moderna.

Palabras clave: derecho administrativo; historia jurídica; inteligencia artificial en el derecho; modernización de la legislación; transformaciones políticas en Medio Oriente.

Introduction

Administrative law, as a branch that regulates the interaction between government institutions and individuals, is a fundamental element of the world's legal systems. Its historical development reflects the evolution of approaches to government management and control, reflecting broader political, social and economic changes in society. For these reasons, the history of administrative law in Jordan demonstrates its ability to adapt to the needs of national and international politics, making it an interesting object of study in the broader context of legal and institutional history.

In the 20th century, administrative law theory began its long journey of transformation from static and formalized rights to flexible forms of regulation that contribute not only to the formal maintenance of norms and rules of order in society, but also promote active public participation and enhance the openness and transparency of government. These transformation processes have become a response to society's demand to modernize public administration and to respond to legitimate demands for more transparent and democratic governance.

Furthermore, an important aspect of the development of the theory of administrative law is its internationalization. With the globalization of economic processes, which are increasingly integrated into international structures, the question of the adaptation of national administrative systems becomes more important and relevant.

At the same time, modern technologies and, in particular, artificial intelligence have posed new challenges to administrative law. The digitization of management processes requires a revision of traditional approaches to transparency, accountability and human rights. Adapting administrative law to these changes is essential to ensure its effectiveness and fairness in the new technological era.

Looking at the example of Jordan, administrative law has undergone a number of significant and fundamental changes, which resulted in the manifestation of internal transformations: political, social and otherwise. The impact of artificial intelligence on Jordan's administrative law is a relatively new phenomenon, but it is already clear how digital technologies influence the country's regulatory practices and management processes. Indeed, administrative law in Jordan is responding to these challenges by adapting its rules and procedures on an ongoing basis, which contributes to the effective inclusion of artificial intelligence in government management structures in general.

Commonly, the role of administrative law in regulating the use of artificial intelligence is becoming increasingly important. Given the potential of AI to transform public administration, Jordan, like many other countries, faces the need to develop legal frameworks that not only address current challenges, but also anticipate future changes. This kind of thinking and foresight is key to creating resilient and adaptable legal systems in an era of rapid technological change.

Epistemologically, the question of studying the history of the development of administrative law, both on an international scale and in the context of specific countries, such as Jordan, remains important and relevant to the community of social scientists and legal scholars. Therefore, this research provides insight into how legal systems adapt to the social, economic and technological changes occurring on a global scale. Similarly, the study of administrative law makes it possible to assess the effectiveness and fairness of public administration and also contributes to the formation of strong democratic institutions that are important for the sustainable development of society.

In theoretical and doctrinal terms, an introductory review of the different works and authors that influenced the development of this research is in order. In his work, Drechsler (2013) focuses on the long process of evolution of administrative law, offering a comparative analysis of Chinese, Western and Islamic governance paradigms. This resource examines the diversity of approaches to administrative law in different cultural and historical contexts, from 1970 to 2000.

At the same time, Correia et al., (2024) consider the challenges posed by the use of artificial intelligence in administrative practices, particularly in the context of smart cities. This source pays attention to the reflections and legal aspects of the introduction of artificial intelligence in the administrative field, between 2000 and 2024. In the same vein, Ladeur (2011) analyzes the evolution of general administrative law and the emergence of a post-

modern approach to it. This research provides a hermeneutic understanding of the changes and trends in administrative law.

Wischmeyer (2020) explores the impact of artificial intelligence on administrative processes, in particular the issues of openness and transparency. He also discusses the importance of transparency and openness in the implementation of digital technologies in administrative processes. An important paper by Bakiner (2023) explores the challenges of reconciling artificial intelligence with human rights, raising awareness of the ethical and legal implications of using these technologies. Definitely, this resource examines the challenges and opportunities of artificial intelligence in the context of human rights from 2023.

In a Jordanian context, Zumbansen (2013) explores the intersection of international and national administrative law, including the symbolic and material dimensions that interact and influence each other. By way of contribution the author examines how globalization influences the formation of administrative structures and procedures in the context of different countries, including Jordan. Similarly, Awaisheh et al. (2023) examine a specific aspect of administrative law: its role in promoting environmental security in Jordan. In addition, the article pays attention to the enforcement mechanisms of administrative law in resolving environmental protection issues and ensuring sustainable development.

In addition, Eman et al. (2023) trace the history of administrative justice in Jordan over more than half a century. This research offers a unique insight into the development of judicial procedures and describes their impact on the country's administrative system during this period. Subsequently, Torki Bani Salameh (2017) provides an analysis of political reforms in Jordan affecting the country's administrative system. The article reveals the internal political dynamics and the implications for the development of administrative law and public administration.

In this state of the art, Al-Hashmi & Al-Nuaimi (2023) conduct a comparative analysis of administrative liability, especially in relation to damage caused by road infrastructure in Jordan. The article examines the legal aspects of administrative liability and its impact on the practical implementation of legislation in the country.

The sources consulted show that despite significant research in the field of law, the analysis of the history of the development of administrative law in Jordan from 1970 to 2024, especially in the context of the challenges posed by artificial intelligence to legal systems, remains poorly understood. This issue requires more and better research to understand how Jordan adapts its administrative and legal structures to the rapid technological change's characteristic of the digital era. Analysis of such adaptations is necessary to determine the effectiveness of legislative and executive responses to AI innovations, which play a key role in modernizing management processes and improving public services.

1. Methodology

In order to successfully achieve the overall objective of the research, two main methods will be used in processing the sources consulted: historical analysis and hermeneutics. The use of a synthesis of these two methods made it possible to interpret, analyze and systematize in detail the historical evolution of administrative law in Jordan, from 1970 to the present. The historical analysis not only identifies key historical stages and periods, but also explored the challenges and changes facing Jordanian administrative law and provides insights on how to address these changes at their place of realization.

Similarly, the use of historical analysis reconstructs the dynamics of key processes in the system of administrative legislation in Jordan, as well as identifies the key factors of influence and change. In turn, through the use of hermeneutics it was possible to carry out a detailed and objective interpretation of the legal and historical texts and other documents of strategic interest in the research. The use of these two methods helped to conduct an in-depth and detailed analysis of the evolution of administrative law in Jordan over a given period. The scope and significance of each method is discussed in more detail below.

The historical analysis method is key in the process of studying the evolution of administrative law in Jordan from 1970 to 2024. This method involved the study of historical events, socio-cultural, political, economic and social changes through the analysis of various historical sources (primary and secondary). The main characteristic of this method is the analysis of space-temporal dynamics. Thus, in the context of analyzing the historical development of administrative law in Jordan, the study began by examining the dynamics of the development of the Jordanian administrative legal system, the political structure and its responses to internal and external changes. This method not only carried out a retrospective analysis, but also, based on the conclusion and systematization of the main consequences, provided insight into possible future trends (prospective analysis) in the development of the legal-administrative system under study.

The main advantage of the historical analysis method is the ability to obtain a systematic understanding of the dynamics of change in a given historical period. In addition, this method reveals the relationship between multidimensional consequences and historical events. In the context of the Jordanian administrative law system and its historical evolution, it was possible to trace how the administrative law system adapts to new challenges and influencing factors, in particular, emphasis was placed on the problems of legal regulation and the use of artificial intelligence technologies.

Despite its significant advantages, the historical method has a number of drawbacks that are worth mentioning. In particular, the application of this method is formed on the basis of the analysis of historical texts and other sources, which can often entail a subjective or biased view of the events of the past: near or distant. Therefore, during the research process, an analysis of different historical sources was carried out in order to reduce the level of subjectivity in the authors of the article.

In this study, hermeneutics was used to interpret a series of statutes, regulations, legal texts and historical sources. The essence of this method is to conduct a thorough analysis of the content of historical and legal sources, taking into account their context and interpretation. A feature of hermeneutics is the use of systematic approaches to the interpretation of legal acts and the establishment of their content. The advantage of the hermeneutic method is the ability to ensure certain accuracy and objectivity in the interpretation of legal sources, through intertextual and contextual dialogue.

Table No. 01. Systematization of the characteristics and key features of the methods selected to carry out the study.

Method of Historical Analysis	Hermeneutics
<p>Disclosure of development trends</p> <p>This method made it possible to identify key trends in the formation and change of administrative law in Jordan, over several historical periods. It also helped to understand which factors influenced the development of the country's management system and which changes were the most significant.</p>	<p>Critique of legal texts</p> <p>The method of hermeneutics makes it possible to systematically examine legal texts according to their context in order to interpret their implications and meanings. This is especially useful for administrative law research, as it helps to reveal various aspects of the legislation and identify its key provisions.</p>
<p>Historical Context</p> <p>Historical analysis can understand the political, social, and economic context of the time, which influences the formation of the legal system. To understand beyond a reasonable doubt, what specific factors influenced legislative changes and reforms.</p>	<p>Comprehension of Historical Texts</p> <p>Hermeneutics makes it possible to understand and interpret historical documents, such as legislative acts, official documents, and political decisions that became the basis for the formation of the modern administrative system. This helps the researcher understand the context and motivation for legislative changes at any particular point in time.</p>
<p>Historical baggage</p> <p>Carrying out a historical analysis under certain material conditions makes it possible to identify not only the reasons and factors for the development of administrative law, but also to assess its patrimony for the administrative succession of the State. This helped to understand which changes have been successful and which will require further successive reforms.</p>	<p>Eliminate misunderstandings</p> <p>The proper use of hermeneutics makes it possible to eliminate misunderstandings and ambiguities in obscure or ambiguous legal texts, which is important for achieving objective and accurate conclusions in research. This can ensure a high level of accuracy and reliability of the results obtained in historical research in general.</p>

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the methodological structure of the research.

In our analysis, we will also consider the impact of artificial intelligence on the development of administrative law in Jordan. Consideration of this aspect helped to understand how technological innovation affects legislation, governance processes and administrative service delivery in the country. The integration of artificial intelligence analysis with historical analysis and hermeneutics clearly shows how digital technologies influence traditional approaches to governance and regulation in Jordan, and how this influences the formation of the modern administrative system in the society.

2. Essence and historical understanding of the development of administrative law

Administrative law, as a branch of law, is concerned with the regulation of interactions between the state and citizens, as well as the internal workings of government agencies in a given society. This area of law provides the framework within which government agencies function not only as legislators or executives, but also as regulators, implementing policies and resolving conflicts. Historically, administrative law developed out of the need to regulate complex governmental structures and guarantee the rights and freedoms of citizens, both dimensions existing in dialectical tension. For these reasons, it plays a key role in ensuring the legality, objectivity and effectiveness of state activities. Administrative law aims to establish government transparency and accountability to citizens (Bryson et al., 2014).

Under current conditions, with the development of technology and globalization, administrative law faces new challenges. The expansion of government activities in areas such as digital information and artificial intelligence requires the adaptation of traditional approaches to regulation and control.

The development of administrative law in many countries occurred under the prism of national reforms, which often involved the revision and modification of legal norms in accordance with changing socioeconomic conditions. This contributed to the creation of legal mechanisms that are more flexible and relevant to the realities of our time. Likewise, administrative law has become a tool to ensure a more effective interaction between the State and society, in the search for a legitimate consensus for the existing social contract. Through a system of administrative procedures and judicial control, it helps to balance the interests of different social groups (Giacinto, 2023).

The introduction of information technologies in public administration processes opens up new opportunities for administrative law. Digitalization makes public services more accessible and convenient for citizens, but it also raises questions about data confidentiality and the protection of personal information. Artificial intelligence as a means to automate decisions in public administration creates the need to review administrative law to ensure the correct use of these technologies, avoid abuses and protect human rights. In Jordan, as in other countries, administrative law is adapting to the new challenges. The reforms initiated in recent decades reflect global trends and aim to improve governance and meet the needs of citizens.

As a synopsis, Fig. 1 shows the evolution of administrative law.

In general, understanding administrative law as a dynamic field responding to modern challenges makes it possible not only to analyze its historical development, but also to predict the directions of future changes. This is especially true for Middle Eastern countries that are experiencing periods of significant transformation and are seeking optimal ways to develop their legal systems in the context of global trends, beyond their historical conflicts.

Figure 1. Doctrinal evolution of administrative law.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

3. Historical Development of Administrative Law in Jordan (1970-1980)

During the 1970s, Jordan was greatly influenced by political and social changes that intensified the development of administrative law. This period marked the end of a long phase of tense relations with Israel and the struggle for political stabilization in the region. In 1971, following the Black September conflict, King Hussein initiated a process of consolidation of power that demanded from the administrative system greater efficiency and transparency in the interaction between government and citizens (Rosenbloom and Abdel-Moneim, 2020).

In 1973, Jordan, responding to the need to modernize the public administration, passed a series of laws aimed at increasing the accountability of civil servants and streamlining management processes. These legislative initiatives are generally aimed at ensuring greater citizen participation in government decisions in the face of democracy and strengthening the legislative framework for combating corruption.

In the mid-1970s, especially in 1976, Jordan experienced economic difficulties, which led the government to introduce additional administrative reforms. These reforms reorganized several important ministries and introduced new administrative regulations to im-

prove the government's interaction with the private sector, which should stimulate economic growth (Macêdo et al., 2021).

The late 1970s and early 1980s were marked by Jordan's growing role on the international scene, which required additional adaptation of administrative law to international standards. In 1979, following the peace treaty between Egypt and Israel, Jordan intensified its diplomatic efforts, which also required reforms in governance mechanisms for effective international cooperation in the Middle East among Arab countries (Abdul Aziz, 2015).

As a result of these changes, administrative law in Jordan until the late 1970s was characterized by strengthened legislative frameworks, improved management structures and a greater emphasis on international integration, which provided the country with the necessary tools to further develop and comply with international obligations in an area of ever-simmering wars and geopolitical conflicts.

In order to carry out a detailed hermeneutical examination of the historical evolution of administrative law in Jordan, during the period from 1970 to 1980, it is important to conduct a detailed analysis of the main laws, regulations and policies that had the most significant impact on administrative management systems in this country during the period under study. Thus, this analysis must begin by taking into account the political and social aspects of Jordanian life, which became the determining factors in the subsequent evolution of administrative law.

Indeed, as of 1970, Jordanian administrative law, which until then had been influenced by the Ottoman and British administrative heritage, began to acquire its own subjectivity and ontological identity. The first step towards this will be the amendment of the Jordanian Constitution, promulgated in 1952. These rights determined the beginning of the transformation processes of Jordan's administrative and legal framework and had as a cross-cutting objective the formation of new management mechanisms that corresponded to the needs and social problems of the time.

The key law in this context was adopted in 1971, Law No. 25, which defined a new period of decentralization of local government management and development. This law was an important step in the vector of democratization of administrative bodies. Its regulation has opened wide opportunities for the population to participate in the development of society, and has also improved the speed and quality of the activities of government bodies. Along with this area, the aforementioned Law introduced significant changes in the activities of state-owned enterprises, forming new management and quality control mechanisms. With the adoption of decentralization rules and regulations, an important aspect of the development of administrative law was the creation of the High Court of Justice, which became the key body for supervising the competence of administrative decisions and ensuring legal accountability in the face of social justice (Table 2).

Table 2. Key legislation that shaped the administrative legal landscape in Jordan during the 1970s.

Law	Characteristics
Act No. 6 of 1972.	This law was enacted to regulate the administration and disposition of State assets, ensuring a more systematic and responsible management of public assets. It outlined procedures for leasing, selling, and managing state property and was crucial in preventing the misuse of state resources and improving the financial accountability of public institutions.
Act No. 17 of 1973.	The Civil Service Act was a landmark reform that established rules and guidelines for the employment, promotion and discipline of civil servants. This law aimed to professionalize the public sector by standardizing recruitment processes, establishing clear job classifications, and establishing merit-based promotion criteria. It had a significant influence on the efficiency and integrity of the Jordanian administrative apparatus.
Law No. 33 of 1976.	The Income Tax Law revised Jordan's tax framework, introducing more progressive tax policies and clearer income tax rules for individuals and legal entities. He played a crucial role in structuring the State's fiscal policy and aligning it with economic growth objectives. The law also included provisions relating to tax resources, which improved legal remedies for taxpayers and contributed to a more transparent tax administration system.
Act No. 12 of 1977.	This legislation established a comprehensive social security system to provide pensions, disability benefits and other social security benefits to workers in the formal sector. It marked a significant step towards social welfare and protection of the Jordanian workforce, laying the groundwork for future expansions of social security coverage.

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the laws consulted during this period.

The 1970s were also characterized by legislative reforms that sought to increase transparency and public participation in administrative processes. These reforms were crucial in establishing a legal framework that supported more effective and equitable governance that underpinned the country's development.

Analysis of these legal reforms reveals their broad impact and effectiveness. Although they were intended to address specific administrative problems, their implementation often faced obstacles, from bureaucratic inertia to political resistance. Through the lens of specific case studies and legal-historical decisions, the nuanced picture of the implementation of these laws and the challenges they faced in their particular context becomes clear (Abadneh *et. al.*, 2023; Alhendi, 2019).

A comparative analysis with Middle Eastern countries provides additional information, placing Jordan's administrative legal evolution in a regional context, but this purpose is beyond the scope of this research. Such a comparison would not only highlight unique national legal trajectories, but would also most certainly shed light on shared challenges and opportunities for collaboration. In conclusion, the 1970s was a decade of significant legal

innovations in Jordan, with a lasting impact on the nation's administrative law. The legacy of the reforms initiated during this period continues to influence Jordanian governance, underscoring the importance of this decade in the region's historical and legal scholarship.

4. Historical Development of Administrative Law in Jordan (1990-2000)

During the 1990s, Jordan experienced a major period of reforms that had a profound impact on administrative law in the country. This period was marked by rapid changes that contributed to the development of the legal system and adaptation to new national and international challenges. At the beginning of the decade, in 1991, following the end of the Cold War and in response to global political changes, Jordan initiated a series of administrative reforms with the aim of modernizing public administration and increasing transparency in interactions between the state and citizens. These reforms included legislative revisions and new regulations that made government services more open and accessible (Demirci, 2016).

In 1994, following the signing of a peace agreement with Israel, Jordan focused on strengthening its international relations and integrating into regional and global economic structures. This required further development of administrative legislation to ensure compliance of national legislation with international standards and treaties. In this context, new laws and regulations are introduced to improve the domestic investment climate and protect foreign investment.

In the late 1990s, Jordan worked actively to attract foreign investment and modernize its economy. In 1997, legislation was passed to simplify licensing and permitting procedures, reducing administrative barriers for new businesses and providing greater legal support for entrepreneurs (Alahbabi, 2024).

During 1999, the Jordanian government passed several important legislative initiatives aimed at strengthening administrative accountability and control. These measures included the creation of new regulatory bodies and the strengthening of the role of the courts in resolving administrative disputes. In particular, stricter rules on transparency and administrative accountability were introduced.

From the turn of the millennium until 2000, Jordan worked actively to create the necessary conditions for integration into a globalized world, which required a corresponding adaptation of administrative law. The reforms introduced during this period paved the way for new technological impacts and challenged Jordan to adapt to future developments in digital technology and artificial intelligence.

By way of summary, Figure No. 02 presents the main transformations of administrative law in Jordan in the period 1970-2000.

Figure 2: Main transformations of administrative law in Jordan in the period 1970-2000.

Source: authors' elaboration (2024).

Thus, between 1970 and 2000, Jordanian administrative law underwent profound transformations, which were reflected in the stabilization of public administration, integration into international structures and modernization of economic policies. Towards the end of 2000, with the growing importance of digital technologies, Jordan was faced with the need to manage the new challenges associated with digitization and artificial intelligence. This required the legal system to adapt to the rapidly evolving technological realities to ensure the protection of citizens' rights and to enable the effective use of new opportunities, highlighting the constant need for innovation and reform in the field of administrative law (see Table 3).

Table 3. Key legislation that shaped the administrative legal landscape in Jordan during the 1990s.

Law	Characteristics
Law No. 10 of 1993.	This law reformed labor regulations, improving worker protections and establishing the framework for labor relations and rights in Jordan. It included provisions on working hours, safety standards and dispute settlement mechanisms. Similarly, the law aimed to balance the rights and responsibilities of employers and employees, fostering a more stable and fair labor market.
Act No. 16 of 1995.	The Environmental Protection Act was a pioneering piece of legislation aimed at regulating activities that could affect the environment. It established guidelines for environmental impact assessments and set penalties for environmental violations. This law was an important step towards integrating environmental considerations into Jordan's economic and administrative planning.
Law No. 25 of 1997.	This law was instrumental in establishing a more favorable environment for local and foreign investment. By providing tax exemptions, customs exemptions, and simplifying administrative procedures, it aimed to stimulate economic growth and diversify the national economy. The law also established the framework for the Jordan Board of Investment, reinforcing its role in attracting and facilitating investment.
Act No. 42 of 1998.	Essentially, this law reformed local governance by giving municipalities greater autonomy and financial resources. Its objective was to improve local administrative capacity, promote local development projects and increase public participation in local decision-making processes.

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the laws consulted during this period.

The early 1990s were a period of rapid and remarkable legal reforms for Jordan, which led to a fundamental reform of the country's administrative environment, bringing it in line with international standards of quality, democracy and transparency. Thus, from 1990 to 2000, several reform laws were adopted concerning the development of labor relations, environmental protection, development of investment activities and local administration, among others. All these regulations marked an important step in the Jordanian government's attempt to embark on the path of liberalization, political modernization and sustainable social development.

For these reasons, the Labor Law was passed in 1993, which became a key reforming legal act for Jordanian labor legislation. This Law provided the legal framework for updating the system for the protection of workers' rights, clarifying working hours, safe working conditions, safety standards for the work environment and other issues. In addition, this Law established rules for conflict resolution and outlined the dynamics of interaction between the employer and the employee. All the changes regulated by the Labor Law have become an important positive factor influencing economic growth and fair employment.

Environmental issues were also addressed in the 1995 Environmental Protection Law, which introduced regulations to safeguard Jordan's natural resources. This law marked a significant shift toward sustainability, making it mandatory to assess the environmental im-

part of projects and establishing strict penalties for violations. It stressed the importance of integrating environmental considerations into economic and administrative planning, reflecting Jordan's growing worldwide awareness of environmental problems, which have led to the phenomenon of global warming.

As a whole, the economic reforms were reinforced by the 1997 Investment Promotion Law, which drastically changed the investment climate in Jordan. By offering incentives such as tax and customs exemptions and simplifying administrative procedures, this law aimed to attract domestic and foreign investments, crucial for the country's economic diversification and growth (Alhendi, 2019). The establishment of the Jordan Investment Board under this law played a key role in facilitating and promoting investment, signaling Jordan's commitment to becoming a competitive player in the global market.

Finally, the Municipalities Law of 1998 reformed local governance by granting municipalities greater autonomy and resources. This law was designed to strengthen local administrative capacities, increase public participation in local decision-making and support localized development projects. By decentralizing power and equipping local governments with the necessary tools to effectively address local needs, this law played a crucial role in promoting balanced regional development (Al-Billeh, 2023).

Taken together, these laws of the 1990s reflect a concerted effort by Jordan to modernize its administrative and legal framework, improving its governance capacity, economic competitiveness and social welfare. This period of legal transformation not only addressed immediate administrative and economic challenges, but also laid a solid foundation for continued reforms in the new millennium, significantly influencing Jordan's trajectory towards a more robust, dynamic and inclusive society.

5. Historical development of administrative law in Jordan (2000-2015)

From 2001 to 2015, Jordan continued its path of major legislative reforms and administrative modernization. This period was characterized by further liberalization of the economy, improvement of legal frameworks to promote transparency and efficiency, and efforts to improve social security and public welfare. One of the most prominent legislative acts of this period was the Investment Law of 2014, which consolidated various investment-related laws into a single framework to simplify the administrative process and encourage both local and foreign investment. This law sought to make Jordan a more attractive destination for investors by offering incentives, reducing bureaucratic hurdles and improving the overall business environment. It established the Jordan Investment Commission, centralizing investment-related services and decision making to improve efficiency and transparency (Box 4).

Table 4. Key legislation that shaped the administrative legal landscape in Jordan during the 2000s.

Law	Characteristics
Amendments to the Labour Act 2010.	This amendment is an update to labor regulations to improve worker protection, align with international labor standards, and address new labor market dynamics. The amendments at this stage focused on improving conditions of employment, working hours, wages and dispute resolution.
Anti-Corruption Commission Act, 2006.	This law established the Anti-Corruption Commission to address administrative corruption within public offices, improving integrity and public trust in government institutions.
Investment Act of 2014.	The investment law reorganized the framework for investments, merging the previous laws into a unified statute to streamline the investment process and encourage local and international investments. It also established the Jordan Investment Commission to centralize investment-related procedures and improve efficiency.
Public-Private Partnerships Act of 2014.	Lay introduced to facilitate and regulate partnerships between government and private sector entities, with the aim of leveraging private expertise and financing for public infrastructure projects and services.

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the laws consulted during this period.

Jordan also updated its labor legislation to better align it with international labor standards. The 2010 amendments to the Labor Law were particularly significant, as they strengthened worker protection, improved labor rights, and addressed the changing dynamics of the workplace. These amendments included better regulation of working hours, employment conditions, and dispute resolution mechanisms, with the goal of creating a more equitable labor market that would lead to greater worker productivity and satisfaction.

Additionally, significant steps were taken to improve public administration and governance (Fraihat *et. al.*, 2023; Alhendi, 2019). The Public-Private Partnership Law of 2014 aimed to facilitate and regulate collaborations between the public sector and private companies in various projects. This law was crucial to leverage private sector expertise and funding in infrastructure and service projects, with the aim of improving the management of public resources and service delivery without overburdening the state budget.

During the period between 2000 and 2024, Jordanian administrative law continued to evolve, adapting to the new challenges arising from the rapid development of digital technologies and artificial intelligence. In 2000, Jordan began implementing a series of legislative initiatives aimed at regulating the use of digital technologies in public administration. Particular attention was paid to data protection and privacy, in response to growing civil society concerns about personal information.

Prior to 2005, due to the spread of Internet and mobile technologies, the Jordanian government took steps to update the infrastructure and legislative framework governing digital communications and commerce. New laws were introduced to ensure the security of electronic transactions and enhance online consumer protection (Al Khalaileh, 2023).

In 2010, in response to the growing influence of artificial intelligence in global markets, Jordan introduced the first regulations to specifically address the use of AI in the financial sector and government services. These measures included the creation of an ethical framework for the development and use of artificial intelligence, as well as the introduction of data security standards.

In 2015, with the increasing reliance on technology, Jordan adopted a cybersecurity strategy encompassing national directives to protect critical infrastructure and ensure national security in the context of growing cyber threats. As we move towards 2020, the Jordanian government has intensified its efforts to digitize the administration. Comprehensive programs were introduced to provide access to government services online, which significantly improved citizens' interaction with the government and contributed to increasing the efficiency of administrative procedures (Al Dalaien and Al Enizi, 2021).

6. Development of administrative law in Jordan in the period 2017-2024, in the context of the formation and influence of artificial intelligence

In 2024, Jordan is focused on adapting its legislative and regulatory framework to the challenges posed by the rapid development of artificial intelligence and automation in public management. New draft laws aimed at creating a balance between innovative development and guaranteeing citizens' rights and freedoms have been developed, reflecting global trends and domestic needs in regulating the latest technologies.

Definitely if one analyzes the issues of artificial intelligence and its impact on the development of administrative law in Jordan, from a historical perspective, it can be said that in recent years it has played a key role in this field. In particular, this is due to the fact that a modern control system simply cannot function without a number of digital technologies and modern methods of processing large amounts of data, the so-called big data.

First, starting in 2017, Jordanian administrative departments began using software that leveraged the analytical capabilities of artificial intelligence to optimize big data processes. This change made it possible to streamline the provision of basic administrative services, as well as significantly reduce the costs of bureaucratic procedures and free some staff from routine work. This, in turn, has greatly increased the level of approval of government institutions by citizens and improved Jordan's position on the international stage. But, at the same time, this use of new software posed a number of challenges to cybersecurity departments, some of which should have been addressed through an updated administrative law framework (Wischmeyer, 2020).

The second important aspect of the impact of artificial intelligence on administrative law is the strengthening of data protection mechanisms. With the increase in the amount of data processed by electronic systems, Jordan has adopted stricter data protection laws introduced to regulate the collection, storage and processing of personal information. These measures are intended to ensure the confidentiality of citizens' personal data, giving them greater control over their own information.

Finally, it should be noted that the development of digital technologies and artificial intelligence has posed a number of challenges to Jordan’s administrative law system, mainly related to the formation of new legal frameworks concerning the safe and legal handling of innovative technologies. Indeed, the Jordanian government is currently actively working on the formation of a new regulatory framework based on the ethical boundaries of the use of AI. In addition, special attention is being paid to the branches of jurisprudence and law enforcement. This tiered establishment of legal frameworks, rules and restrictions can become a guarantor of the safe use of artificial intelligence technologies, in which the rights and freedoms of citizens will be strictly respected and the interests of the state will be realized (Kay, 2024).

Figure 3 shows the main aspects of the impact of artificial intelligence on administrative law in Jordan.

Figure 3. Main stages of the impact of AI on administrative law in Jordan.

Source: Prepared by the authors as a result of the hermeneutic work of the sources consulted.

As argued, between 2000 and 2024, Jordan witnessed significant changes in the field of administrative law, which will be significantly complicated by the influence of artificial intelligence. The development of digital technologies has opened up new opportunities for governments and citizens, but requires corresponding legal and policy reforms to ensure the protection of rights and the effective use of innovations. This section of the study underscores the need to continuously adapt legal frameworks to rapid technological changes and highlights the importance of ethical standards in the use of artificial intelligence to ensure fair and effective administration for all.

Conclusions

The global changes of the last fifty years have brought about significant transformations in the administrative legal systems of many countries around the world. Since the 1970s, there has been a transformation of administrative legal systems around the world towards greater transparency and democracy, as well as the formation of new legal norms relating to innovation in economics and technology.

Indeed, in the early 1970s, a large number of countries, including Jordan, were facing problems of social instability and the consequences of global crisis phenomena on their economies. This situation forced the regulatory state to extend the scope of legal regulation to almost all areas of human life. This led to the formation of a series of new laws and the transformation of policies in the Middle East. In later years, the phenomena of globalization and internationalization brought about changes in administrative law and pushed for adaptation to international norms and standards. From then until today, most modern Western-type societies have established active cooperative ties on environmental issues, regulation of international market relations, cybersecurity and other strategic issues.

In the new millennium, technology is playing an increasingly important role in shaping administrative action. Digital innovations, such as e-governance, online services and data analytics, are changing the way governments interact with citizens and favor efficient administration. However, this requires administrative law to constantly adapt to new challenges and respect the principles of fairness, transparency and protection of human rights.

Jordanian administrative law has come a long way in the last five decades, characterized by reform and adaptation to new challenges and opportunities, which does not mean that it is not without contradictions. The development of administrative law between 1970 and 2000 was accompanied by rapid economic growth and the modernization of public administration, which required the introduction of new legislative rules and control mechanisms. Between 2000 and 2024, Jordan witnessed the significant impact of digital technologies and artificial intelligence on administrative processes. Artificial intelligence has played a key role in streamlining public administration and providing better services to citizens, while strengthening data protection and privacy.

Globally, from 1970 to the present, administrative law has traveled a difficult road of adapting to new societal challenges, such as globalization, technological development and changes in the political and economic situation in each region of the world. This has led to a change of emphasis in the legal system and increased regulation in many areas of everyday life of ordinary people.

When scientifically considering the development of administrative law in Jordan, it is important to take into account the high level of dynamics of the development of society, as well as the impact on it and, consequently, the requirements for administrative law in relation to technological progress, digital technologies and artificial intelligence. So the modern system of administrative law, taking into account its historical development and current requirements, should be flexible, adaptable and formed on the basis of a detailed understanding of modern social, economic and technological processes.

It should also be noted that in the process of historical analysis of the evolution of administrative law in Jordan, a key trend was observed that continues to this day. Thus, the vector of the modern administrative law system in Jordan aims to find the optimal balance between ensuring the realization of the key interests of society and the needs of citizens and, at the same time, strengthening the capabilities and resource base of the state.

This balance in Jordan is often achieved through the use of modern digital technologies, particularly artificial intelligence. However, this active participation of innovations in the system of administrative law requires the formation of qualitatively new legal regulations to protect the rights and freedoms of all participants in public relations. Everything indicates that, permanent and effective analysis and subsequent adaptation of new realities and technologies to administrative law will enable the latter to fulfill its main epistemological functions and tasks as a knowledge serving the maintenance of public order and management of social conflict between different interests and needs.

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